

Information sheet 1.03

Chemical treatments on crops including reproductive material

This information sheet is a supporting document to Appendix A ('Standardised checklist of risk reduction options') of the Guidance of the EFSA Plant Health Panel on quantitative pest risk assessment.

EFSA PLH Panel (EFSA Panel on Plant Health), Jeger M, Bragard C, Caffier D, Candresse T, Chatzivassiliou E, Dehnen-Schmutz K, Grégoire J-C, Jaques Miret JA, MacLeod A, Navajas Navarro M, Niere B, Parnell S, Potting R, Rafoss T, Rossi V, Urek G, Van Bruggen A, Van der Werf W, West J, Winter S, Hart A, Schans J, Schrader G, Suffert M, Kertész V, Kozelska S, Mannino MR, Mosbach-Schulz O, Pautasso M, Stancanelli G, Tramontini S, Vos S and Gilioli G, 2018. Guidance of the EFSA PLH Panel on quantitative pest risk assessment. EFSA Journal 2018;16(7):5350, 94 pp. doi:10.2903/j.efsa.2018.5350. Available online at <https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2018.5350>

This document is currently still under preparation and will be made available in the near future.